

References

1. The Wealth of India, "Raw Material", C. S. I. R. New Delhi. Vol 1, 1948, p. 66.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. I, 2nd edition, p. 752.
3. I. HEILBORN, H. M. BUNBURY, A. H. COOK and E. R. H. JONES, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", (Eyre Spottwood, London), 1965, Vol. 5, pp. 2902, 3093.
4. K. PEACH and M. V. TRACEY, "Modern Methods of Plant Analysis", (Springer Verlag, Berlin) 1955, Vol. 3A, pp. 167, 471.
5. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAN and N. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", 1970, p. 41.
6. K. A. ZIRVI, K. JEWERS and M. J. NAGLER, "Phytochemical Investigation of *Prosopis glandulosa* stem", *Planta Medica*, Nov. 1977, p. 240.

**Chemical Investigation of Pod Husk of
Cassia auriculata Linn**

D. R. LOHAR,* S. P. GARG and D. D. CHAWAN**

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 23 July 1980, revised 27 January 1981,
accepted 9 June 1981

CASSIA auriculata Linn. is a small perennial shrub growing wild in Rajasthan and Central India and is well known for its medicinal and economic values¹. It has been studied for its flavonoids²⁻⁴, tannins⁵, anthraquinones⁶ and certain proteolytic enzymes^{7,8}. The present paper deals with the isolation and identification of chrysophanol, emodin and rubiadin from pod husk of the plant. Though chrysophanol and emodin have been reported from several *Cassia* species, rubiadin has not so far been reported from any.

The chloroform extract of powdered pod husk, after removing petroleum ether fraction, was chromatographed over silica-gel column using benzene and chloroform in varying proportions as eluent. It yielded four compounds one of which was a white crystalline compound identified as β -sitosterol, already reported from this plant. The three other compounds had melting points 196°, 256° and 301°.

The yellow coloured compound m.p. 196°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+254) gave orange-red colour with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹ and red colour with sodium dithionate in alkaline solution¹⁰. Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a 1, 8-dihydroxy anthraquinone (1625 cm^{-1} for chelated carbonyl and 1670 cm^{-1} for non-chelated carbonyl)¹¹. The compound was identified as chrysophanol (1, 8-dihydroxy-3 methyl anthraquinone) by m.m.p. and co-tlc of acetyl and methyl derivatives with authentic samples.

The second orange coloured compound m.p. 256°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_5$ (M^+270) gave pink colour with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹ and red colour with sodium dithionate in alkaline solution¹⁰.

Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a dihydroxy anthraquinone with one free OH group at position 2, 3, 6 or 7 (3390 cm^{-1} free -OH; 1670 cm^{-1} non-chelated C=O; 1625 cm^{-1} chelated C=O)¹¹. The compound was identified as emodin (1,6,8-trihydroxy-3-methyl anthraquinone) by m.m.p., co-tlc and ir.

The third yellow coloured compound, m.p. 310° $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ (M^+254) gave positive tests with methanolic magnesium acetate⁹. Ultraviolet and infrared spectra suggested it to be a 1, 3-dihydroxy anthraquinone (3420 cm^{-1} , free -OH; 1650 cm^{-1} non-chelated carbonyl, and 1625 cm^{-1} chelated carbonyl group)¹¹. It was identified as rubiadin by m.m.p., co-tlc and ir of its acetyl and methyl derivatives with those of an authentic specimen. Rubiadin is thus reported for the first time in *Cassia* species.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor, Head, Department of Chemistry for providing the facilities and to Dr. P. N. Varma, Director, Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia Laboratory, Ghaziabad for critically going through the manuscript. One of the authors (D.R.L.) is thankful to CSIR for a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, C. S. I. R. Pub. 1956, p. 54.
2. Y. M. THERESA, K. V. BHANU and Y. NAYUDAMMA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 1623.
3. K. R. S. REDDY, G. SRIMANNARAYANA and M. V. SURBA RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 956.
4. R. R. PORIS and B. CUBUKAU, *Ann. Pharm. Franc.*, 1961, 20, 583.
5. P. HANUMANTA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ind. & News. Ed.* 1952, 15, 187.
6. L. NIHOUL, *J. Pharm. Belg.*, 1960, 15, 49.
7. W. MADHAVAKRISHNA, S. M. BOSE and Y. NAYUDAMMA, *Bull. Cent. Leather Res. Inst. Madras*, 1960, 7, 1.
8. S. C. DHAR and S. M. BOSE, *Leather Sci.*, 1965, 12, 54.
9. S. SHIBATA, M. TAKIDO and O. TANAKA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2789.
10. F. FRIGL, "Spot test in Organic Analysis", Elsevier Pub. Co. Inc., New York, 1966, 336.
11. M. BLOOM, L. H. BRIGGS and B. CLEVERLEY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 178.

**A Note on the Antibacterial Action of Some
2-Anilinoacetyl-5-Nitrofurans**

B. SHIVARAMA HOLLA and SARVOTTAM Y. AMBEKAR*

Department of Chemistry, University of Mysore,
Mysore-570 006

and

B. G. PUJAR

Department of Chemistry, Karnataka University,
Dharwar-3

Manuscript received 2 February 1981, accepted 9 June 1981

It has been shown by Sherman¹ that compounds in which the nitrofur ring is directly attached to a heterocyclic ring exhibit antibacterial activity. Since then a number of nitrofuryl heterocycles have

* Present address : Homoeopathic Pharmacopoeia Laboratory, Central Government Offices Complex, Hapur Road, Ghaziabad-201 002.

** Department of Botany, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001.

* For correspondence.